

Using SVMs to detect images hidden within images or videos (Steganalysis)

1st Davaughn Hoots
 Department of Computer Sciences
 Montclair State University
 Montclair, United States
 hootsd1@montclair.edu

Abstract—We will be looking at the process in which a user can hide images in video frames, and how we will be using SVMs in order to determine if an image falls under one of two classifications. Clean or altered.

Fig. 1. Flow chart of the process we will be trying to achieve throughout this project

I. INTRODUCTION

The focus of this project is to use SVMs to aid in steganalysis to detect images that have been hidden in videos using steganography.

The following graphic illustrates steganalysis:

Fig. 2. Shows how steganalysis and steganography are related

Fig. 3. shows an image hidden inside of another image using steganography

Hidden images in videos can contain explicit or confidential material that can be uploaded to a public site such as YouTube

as mass distributed to a specific audience without being detected

II. PROBLEM DEFINITION AND ALGORITHM

A. Task Definition

The following is a breakdown of how a person would insert hidden images into a video file to understand what we are trying to achieve.

A user breaks down a video into video frames and hides images among the video frames using steganography.

We can use an online steganography tool to hide an image inside of another image or video frame for our project we will be using

<https://incoherency.co.uk/image-steganography/##>

Then finally render the video frames back into a video containing the hidden images.

Fig. 4. Demonstrates the process of turning videos into altered videos with hidden images inside of them.

From there you can upload the video to YouTube where people can simply convert the video to video frames and then decode the hidden images.

This process leaves us with two types of images that we can look for, clean images that do not contain any hidden images and then altered images where our hidden images are stored.

B. Algorithm Definition

1) SVM: There are two types of SVM: Linear SVM: Linear SVM is used for data that are linearly separable i.e. for a dataset that can be categorized into two categories by utilizing a single straight line.

Fig. 5. Showing the difference between a “clean” image and an altered one.

Non-linear SVM: Non-Linear SVM is used for data that are non-linearly separable data i.e. a straight line cannot be used to classify the data-set.

Fig. 6. Showing the difference between Linearly Separable Data and Non-linearly Separable Data

We are going to utilize a linear SVM for image type detection.

2) *Data-set:* The Genome Project Stanford database contains 70,000 monochromatic still images containing 8 features, which are classified into two classes based on LSB steganographic techniques (1) and without LSB steganographic techniques (0)

Please visit the following link for more details:

<https://iee-dataport.org/open-access/steganalysis-still-images-lsb-steganography-features-dataset>

3) *Levels of alteration:* Steganographic algorithms can encode five types of payloads, ranging from 0.1 to 0.5 They will be listed and shown as

Fig. 7. Shows all the levels of Alteration. With two extra levels as an example of what can be seen by the naked eye

For demonstration purposes we include 2 further levels of alteration, but these are not used in practice.

4) *Implementation:* First we will look at the important python libraries that will be used for this project and explain their importance.

Sklearn: Scikit-learn is a free machine learning library for Python. It features various algorithms like support vector machine, random forests, and k-neighbors, and it also supports Python numerical and scientific libraries like NumPy and SciPy

Joblib: Joblib is a set of tools to provide lightweight pipelining in Python. In particular:

transparent disk-caching of functions and lazy re-evaluation (memoize pattern) and easy simple parallel computing

Joblib is optimized to be fast and robust on large data in particular and has specific optimizations for NumPy arrays. We will first train our SVM model against our database of 70,000 images containing 8 features. The following SVM implementation will be utilized for this project.

Sklearn’s SVM - Sklearn’s implementation is used to train the SVM model.

```
def create_svm_classifier(joblib_file):
    ...
    Train SVM classifier with training set (feature vectors) from csv file,
    and load the trained model in .joblib file
    ...
    start_time = time.time()
    classifier = svm.SVC(kernel = 'linear', C=1, gamma='auto')
    classifier.fit(x_train, y_train) # fit svm classifier to the train data
    Runtime.append(time.time() - start_time)

    print("SVM classifier:")

    print("Accuracy on train set: ", classifier.score(x_train, y_train))
    AccuracyTrain.append(classifier.score(x_train, y_train))

    print("Accuracy on test set: ", classifier.score(x_test, y_test))
    AccuracyTest.append(classifier.score(x_test, y_test))

    joblib.dump(classifier, joblib_file) # save classifier in the joblib file
```

Fig. 8. Code implementation of SVM Classifier creation

```
create_svm_classifier('trained_classifiers/svm-classifier.joblib')
```

Fig. 9. Code implementation of the code which creates and saves the classifier

Once our model has been trained and tested will feed it multiple versions of the same image and see whether our SVM can detect whether the image has been altered or not.

```
SVM classifier:
Accuracy on train set: 0.9048733013089519
Accuracy on test set: 0.9029930709336381
```

Fig. 10. Results of classifier training on our Training and Test data set

After running our implementation we are left with an accuracy of 90

III. FEATURES AND PROCESSING

The feature set includes Kurtosis, Skewness, Standard Deviation, Range, Median, Geometric Mean, Hjorth Mobility,

and Hjorth Complexity, which are all extracted from the histograms of the still images, including random spatial transformations.

A. Kurtosis

In research from Wikipedia contributors (2022, "1" section) In probability theory and statistics, kurtosis (from the ancient Greek feminine noun , "curvature"), also translated as sharpness coefficient 1, flatness coefficient, and degree of curvature, is a direct measure of sharpness and an indirect measure of the flattening of the distribution of a real random variable. There are several measures of acuity, and kurtosis corresponds to Pearson's method.

It is the second of the form parameters, with the asymmetry coefficient (parameters based on moments of order 5 and above have no proper name).

It measures, disregarding the dispersion (given by the standard deviation), the distribution of probability masses around their center, given by the mathematical expectation, that is, in a way, their concentration near or far from the center of probability.

Fig. 11. The above figure represents some symmetric reduced centered unimodal density distributions

B. Skewness

Wikipedia contributors noted that (2022b) Skewness is a measure of the asymmetry of the probability distribution of a real-valued random variable about its mean. The skewness value can be positive, zero, negative, or undefined.

C. Standard Deviation

In research from Wikipedia contributors (2022c) In statistics, the standard deviation is a measure of the amount of variation or dispersion of a set of values.[1] A low standard deviation indicates that the values tend to be close to the mean (also called the expected value) of the set, while a high standard deviation indicates that the values are spread out over a wider range.

Fig. 12. A general relationship of mean and median under differently skewed unimodal distribution

Fig. 13. Example of samples from two populations with the same mean but different standard deviations. The red population has a mean of 100 and an SD of 10; the blue population has a mean of 100 and an SD of 50.

D. Range

In research from Wikipedia contributors (2022d) In statistics, the range of a set of data is the difference between the largest and smallest values.[1] The difference here is specific, the range of a set of data is the result of subtracting the sample maximum and minimum.

However, in descriptive statistics, this concept of range has a more complex meaning. The range is the size of the smallest interval (statistics) which contains all the data and provides an indication of statistical dispersion. It is measured in the same units as the data. Since it only depends on two of the observations, it is most useful in representing the dispersion of small data sets.[2]

E. Median

In research from Wikipedia contributors (2022d) in statistics and probability theory, the median is the value separating the higher half from the lower half of a data sample, a population, or a probability distribution. For a data set, it may be thought of as "the middle" value. The basic feature of the median in describing data compared to the mean (often simply described as the "average") is that it is not skewed by a small proportion of extremely large or small values, and therefore provides a better representation of a "typical" value. Median income, for example, may be a better way to suggest what a "typical"

income is because income distribution can be very skewed. The median is of central importance in robust statistics, as it is the most resistant statistic, having a breakdown point of 50

F. Geometric Mean

In research from Wikipedia contributors (2022f) in mathematics, the geometric mean is a mean or average, which indicates the central tendency or typical value of a set of numbers by using the product of their values (as opposed to the arithmetic mean which uses their sum). The geometric mean is defined as the nth root of the product of n numbers, i.e., for a set of numbers x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n , the geometric mean is defined as

$$\left(\prod_{i=1}^n x_i\right)^{\frac{1}{n}} = \sqrt[n]{x_1 x_2 \cdots x_n}$$

Fig. 14. Mathematics representation of the Geometric Mean

G. Hjorth parameters

In research from Wikipedia contributors (2021), Hjorth parameters are indicators of statistical properties used in signal processing in the time domain introduced by Bo Hjorth in 1970.[1] The parameters are Activity, Mobility, and Complexity. They are commonly used in the analysis of electroencephalography signals for feature extraction. The parameters are normalized slope descriptors (NSDs) used in EEG. Moreover, in the robotic area, the Hjorth parameters are used for tactile signal processing for the physical object properties detection such as surface textures/material detection and touch modality classification via artificial robotic skin.[2]

We use two Hjorth parameters in this project:

1) *Hjorth Mobility*: The mobility parameter represents the mean frequency or the proportion of standard deviation of the power spectrum. This is defined as the square root of the variance of the first derivative of the signal $y(t)$ divided by the variance of the signal $y(t)$.

$$\text{Mobility} = \sqrt{\frac{\text{var}\left(\frac{dy(t)}{dt}\right)}{\text{var}(y(t))}}$$

Fig. 15. Mathematics representation of the Hjorth Mobility

2) *Hjorth Complexity*: The Complexity parameter represents the change in frequency. The parameter compares the signal's similarity to a pure sine wave, where the value converges to 1 if the signal is more similar.

$$\text{Complexity} = \frac{\text{Mobility}\left(\frac{dy(t)}{dt}\right)}{\text{Mobility}(y(t))}$$

Fig. 16. Mathematics representation of the Hjorth Complexity

IV. WORKING EXAMPLE

First we will define a function called StegoOrClean which takes in an image and our trained classifier, and then it returns whether or not the image is clean or stego (altered).

```
def stego_or_clean(img_path, classifier):
    """
    ... This function returns the type of the image: either clean or stego, using the chosen classifier
    ...
    im = cv2.imread(img_path)
    vals = im.mean(axis=2).flatten()
    # plot histogram with 255 bins
    b, bins, patches = plt.hist(vals, 255)
    data = {'kurtosis': [kurtosis(b)],
           'skewness': [skew(b)],
           'std': [std(b)],
           'Range': [ptp(b)],
           'Median': [median(b)],
           'Geometric Mean': [stats.gmean(b)],
           'Mobility': [eeglib.features.hjorthMobility(b)],
           'Complexity': [eeglib.features.hjorthComplexity(b)]
          }
    df = pd.DataFrame(data)
    print(df)
    testing_data = pd.read_csv('train_test_datasets/features_test_70000.csv')
    x_test, y_test = testing_data.drop(['Tag'], axis=1), testing_data['Tag']
    x_test = x_test.append(df, ignore_index=True)
    scaler = preprocessing.MinMaxScaler(feature_range=(0, 1))
    x_test = scaler.fit_transform(x_test)
    return 'stego' if classifier.predict([x_test[13999]])[0] == 1 else 'clean'
```

Fig. 17. Code implementation of the function which will pass our image to our classifier and return a result.

```
#choose an image to apply the steganalysis using the chosen classifier
stego_or_clean('C:/Users/Owner/Downloads/steganalysis-ml-main/steganalysis-ml-main/image.jpg', svm_classifier)
```

Fig. 18. Code implementation of calling the function

First, our SVM will be tested against a clean image.

Fig. 19. shows a demonstration of what happens when we run a clean image through our SVM.

It returns a histogram showing the range of pixels along with the clean classification.

Next, our SVM will be tested against a altered image.

Fig. 20. shows a demonstration of what happens when we run a altered image through our SVM.

It returns a histogram showing the range of pixels along with the stego classification.

V. FUTURE WORK

In the future code optimizations for feeding in multiple images at once and implementing parallel processing in order to check multiple images at a time. Possibly including a queue system to group frames into batches so that parallel processing can be achieved without worrying about causing a deadlock or repeated checks.

A larger training set with high resolution images would yield better results, and possibly even a higher accuracy rate.

VI. CONCLUSION

This project demonstrated a working model of how an SVM can be utilized to detect hidden images inside of other images using steganalysis.

REFERENCES

- [1] Miranda, J. M. (2019, November 21). STEGANALYSIS FOR STILL IMAGES WITH LSB STEGANOGRAPHY - FEATURES DATASET. <https://iee-dataport.org/>. Retrieved April 30, 2022, from <https://iee-dataport.org/open-access/steganalysis-still-images-lsb-steganography-features-dataset>
- [2] Wikipedia contributors. (2022, February 13). Kurtosis. <https://wikipedia.org/>. <https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kurtosis>
- [3] Wikipedia contributors. (2022b, April 7). Skewness. Wikipedia. Retrieved April 30, 2022, from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Skewness>
- [4] Wikipedia contributors. (2022c, April 21). Standard deviation. Wikipedia. Retrieved April 30, 2022, from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Standard_deviation
- [5] Wikipedia contributors. (2022d, April 23). Range (statistics). Wikipedia. Retrieved April 30, 2022, from [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Range_\(statistics\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Range_(statistics))
- [6] Wikipedia contributors. (2022d, April 23). Median. Wikipedia. Retrieved April 30, 2022, from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Median>
- [7] Wikipedia contributors. (2022f, May 1). Geometric mean. Wikipedia. Retrieved April 30, 2022, from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Geometric_mean

- [8] Wikipedia contributors. (2021, May 13). Hjorth parameters. Wikipedia. Retrieved April 30, 2022, from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hjorth_parameters##Hjorth_Mobility
- [9] Wikipedia contributors. (2021, May 13). Hjorth parameters. Wikipedia. Retrieved April 30, 2022, from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hjorth_parameters##Hjorth_Complexity
- [10] sklearn.svm.SVC. (2021, December 23). Scikit-Learn. <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.svm.SVC.html>